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Research Protocol for the Scoping Review “Higher Education Governance”

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1 Abstract

This research protocol provides a detailed description of the procedure for implementing the methodology of a systematic literature assessment, specifically a scoping review. To provide an overview of gender research on university and higher education governance, the scoping review extracted a corpus of 50 studies that were identified by using a specific search strategy in 30 relevant gender research journals which use English as publication language. The overarching scope of the review includes approaches, theories, and methodologies with an intersectional perspective as a tool which is critical of power-relations. Our understanding of governance covers both intra-organizational and inter-organizational governance of universities. This scoping review examines the variety of use and application of theories and methods that examine in which way intersecting, oppressive and gendered hierarchies are embedded into macro-, meso- and micro-levels of governmental structures in universities and higher education institutions. This perspective presents itself as crucial in the layered analysis of national laws, political trends and climate, policies and programs, and leadership and management decisions. The mapping contributes to a better understanding of the scholarly discourse found in the format of journal articles that form the relation of gender studies research with other academic disciplines, e.g. higher education research, in terms of both topical matter and perspective.

2 Introduction

This research protocol forms part of a set of three scoping reviews conducted as part of the GendAReview project: Systematic Reviews – Gender Research Perspectives on Academia and Universities, implemented by CEWS *Center for Gender Relations in Academia* at the *GESIS Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences*. The project is funded for a period of 16 months (December 2024 to March 2026) by the German Federal Ministry of Research, Technology and Space (BMFTR, project no. 16RBM1015). To explore the established theories and methods used by gender research studies analyzing academia, and represented in international journals, the project team conducted scoping reviews on three core areas of higher education research: (1) knowledge production in universities, (2) governance of universities and institutions of higher education and (3) the academic labor market. This scoping review protocol documents the process of our examination of approaches, theories, and methodologies of international gender research studies in the context of higher education and university governance.

Scoping reviews are designed to close knowledge gaps or provide a broad overview of a topic (Elm et al., 2019). A scoping review can lead to thorough insights in interdisciplinary fields of research such as gender or higher education research (Belingheri et al., 2021; Mour, 2022; Raja et al., 2023; Wegner, 2024). The inclusion of mixed-method and multi-method studies, qualitative case studies, and theoretical contributions is particularly useful when the aim of the review is a mapping exercise, and the thematic scoping is based on a specific research question. Nevertheless, the results of a review should always be regarded as preliminary, since research fields are highly dynamic and constantly evolving (Wetterich & Plänitz, 2021).

The umbrella term "gender studies" encompasses perspectives and theories that address socio-cultural, political, and economic issues with reference to gender, sex or inequality. Gender research is an interdisciplinary academic discipline and transdisciplinary field of research. Interdisciplinary gender research examines a wide range of gender-related research questions, approaches, and perspectives (D'Ignazio & Klein, 2020; Kortendiek et al., 2017). In addition, methodological issues are

addressed and critically reflected both within and outside the social sciences (Hunt et al., 2022; Tannenbaum et al., 2019). The interdisciplinary nature of gender research studies is reflected in the scope descriptions of the journals that form the corpus of the present scoping review.

We would like to stress that gender studies, higher education research, and science and technology studies are highly heterogeneous academic disciplines and fields that do not necessarily share a joint set of theories or methodologies. In many academic fields, including higher education research, there is a lack of systematic and consistent reflection, consideration, and analysis of gender-theoretical approaches and perspectives (Ramirez et al., 2021). One indication of this is the lack of relevant literature in the organs of German-language higher education research (Nelson & Zippel, 2021; Ramirez et al., 2021). This is the starting point for our project. The GendAReview research project, within the framework of which the scoping review is being conducted, maps out evidence on theories and methodologies of international gender research studies which could be taken up in German higher education research. The overall goal of the project is to contribute to closing the gaps in expertise on gender theories, such as intersectionality theory, feminist standpoint theory, or queer theory, in future higher education research. Concerning research on academia, it is essential to discern between higher education and science and technology studies. While the German Science Council criticizes the "national self-centeredness" of empirical higher education research in Germany (Wissenschaftsrat, 2014, p. 20), characterized as "inward looking" and assessed by international observers as having little relevance to international debates and being insufficiently comparative (Kosmützky, 2017, p. 34) in the field of science and technology studies a highly international research community has been established.

The scoping review focusing on governance structures in universities and institutions of higher education responds to the following question: What are the established perspectives, theories and methodologies used by the international gender research community to understand university and higher education governance? Intersectional approaches of analysis are of particular concern. By looking at university and higher education governance specifically from a gender research perspective, this work aims to inspire the development of new research perspectives and content for the German-speaking community of higher education research. Furthermore, the review facilitates connection with international debates on academic governance structures and equity and diversity policies.

Intersectionality is an important concept for our research, coined by civil rights activist and scholar of law Kimberlé Crenshaw. Crenshaw developed the concept in the late 1990s in the context of legal disputes involving black women in discriminatory employment relations (Crenshaw, 2003). Crenshaw describes intersectionality as an analytical lens through which the overlap, intertwining, overlap and collision of power structures becomes visible. Intersectionality thus reveals how different social categories — such as gender, ethnicity, and class — interact and influence each other simultaneously. This is not simply a matter of different forms of discrimination existing side by side or being stacked on top of each other and "added together," (Simien, 2007, p. 265), but rather a complex web of social positionings that can only be understood through their mutual constitution. Intersectionality has been taken up and reflected upon in numerous academic disciplines (Davis, 2020). And while some see it as an opportunity to establish a new field of study (Cho et al., 2013), it is often used as a buzzword in contemporary social science analysis without taking its conceptual requirements into account (Davis, 2008). In her publication *Difference That Power Makes: Intersectionality and Participatory Democracy*, however, Patricia Hill Collins criticizes the conceptual vagueness of the frequently used term "power" in intersectionality theory. She argues that "power" often serves merely as a placeholder to describe a deeper system of oppression that actually underlies intersectional theory (Collins, 2017). According to Simien (2007), this system is characterized by the simultaneity and intertwining ("simultaneity of oppression") (Simien, 2007, p. 265) of various dimensions of oppression. The term "systems" emphasizes that the mechanisms of oppression are

structurally embedded - for example, in laws, political measures, cultural norms, and institutions, including universities. They operate on several levels simultaneously: individually, culturally, institutionally, and structurally. A central concern of intersectional theory is to show that social groups are not homogeneous, even though they are often treated as such. Intersectionality not only refers to individual identity characteristics but can also be applied to professional positions within universities. As recent studies show, habitus is used for hierarchization processes in which individuals can only rise to privileged positions by adopting the normalized habitus (Bourabain, 2024; Nascimento Rocha et al., 2024). Those who do not embody the characteristics of the "ideal scientist", such as early-career researchers, are given less voice, which structurally disadvantages these groups.

To operationalize the topical scope of university and higher education governance for our review, we use the following definition:

Governance generally encompasses the entirety of collective regulations that address a specific problem or social issue and are justified with reference to the collective interest of the affected group (Schuppert & Zürn, 2008, p. 28f.). Specifically for science and research, various organizational autonomies can be derived on this basis, including academic freedom. Universities and research institutions determine the structure of decision-making processes, resources, and incentives for their members (cf. Jungbauer-Gans et al., 2023, p. 45). Following *the governance equalizer* five regulatory mechanisms can be distinguished (Lange & Schimank, 2007; Schimank, 2007): state regulation, competition, external stakeholder guidance, academic self-governance, and managerial self-governance, whereby hybrid forms reflect the reality of governance. Our understanding of governance includes controlling dynamics between universities and governmental, financial, inter-(national) associations, and stakeholder groups, whereby the reference to the "organization" (university) must always be given (cf. Oberschelp, 2023, p. 23).

We approached the implementation of this work with several assumptions, based on key literature about the interconnection and differences between gender research and higher education research (Auferkorte-Michaelis & Latta, 2025; Crisp et al., 2024; Nichols & Stahl, 2019; Ramirez et al., 2021; Woodward & Woodward, 2015). Our assumptions or hypotheses led to the formulation of the research aim and question. We assume that, in contrast to higher education research, gender studies research generally includes a discussion of power differentials among the populations under study within a system or between epistemic systems, with oftentimes qualitative methodological approaches. This follows a tradition of feminist-critical social analysis, which is rich in theory and conceptual modelling. In contrast, we expect relatively few system-critical approaches in higher education research, and only marginal expertise in intersectional gender aspects, but rather a stronger service orientation in (commissioned) studies that offer practice-oriented solutions to problems. A perspective that is critical of power-relations tends to be considered only marginally within the discipline (Grzanka et al., 2025). Finally, we assume that higher education research tends to be strongly reliant on quantitative statistical analysis in its methodology and can be described as rather weak in terms of the theorization and conceptualization of gender (Hamann & Kosmützky, 2021).

Nevertheless, despite their differences, the two disciplines align as they share significant similarities: A close examination reveals their inherent interdisciplinary character, manifesting in both the scope of their respective fields and the nature of their subject matters. It is particularly noteworthy that both disciplines are often grounded in a strong sociological foundation and tradition. A high degree of methodological and data diversity is also exhibited by both disciplines (ibid).

3 Methodology

The scoping review is a form of a systematic review that first appeared in the health sciences in the 1970s. Systematic reviews were popularized primarily by groups such as Cochrane and the Johanna Briggs Institute, JBI (Munn et al., 2018; Peters et al., 2020). The review documented here will use the JBI methodology for scoping reviews (Pollock et al., 2024). The essential elements of a scoping review include title and author information, the objective of the review, the inclusion criteria, the methods, and the conclusion. The review title, research question, and development of search strings are based on JBI's framework for scoping reviews (Elm et al., 2019). The framework includes information on the intended review's population, concept, and context and serves as a support tool for formulating clear and precise questions and titles, as well as for developing search string categories (ibid.).

The implementation of the systematic review methodology is further supported by the PRISMA checklist and flow diagram, a protocol that guides the process of conducting and reporting systematic reviews and meta-analyses (Moher et al., 2009). The standardized process tools were developed with the objective of ensuring transparency of the review process by documenting each step of the procedure. In addition, the PRISMA statement facilitates the reproducibility of the review process (Page et al., 2021; Tricco et al., 2018). In 2018, an extension of the PRISMA statement for scoping reviews was published. While systematic reviews are designed to answer a specific and narrow research question, scoping reviews address broader questions and aim to provide an overview of the existing literature or a research gap. Items and criteria of the initial checklist were revised to align with the research objectives of scoping reviews (Tricco et al., 2018). In this scoping review, the items of the PRISMA checklist with the extension for scoping reviews (PRISMA_{scr}) are used for the implementation and documentation of the process, which was technically supported by the EPPI-Software. The PRISMA flow diagram is used to document the study selection. For the present protocol of the scoping review, we use both the scoping review guidelines and the PRISMA template (Barisoux et al., 2024; Lely et al., 2023; Tricco et al., 2018).

3.1 Research Question

The development of the research question for this scoping review was the result of an iterative process. First, the research team formulated a basic research question. The question was discussed with gender and higher education experts, the project's board of experts, whose expertise enriched the implementation of the scoping review, and was revised several times until it met the content-related and all methodological quality criteria. Thus, the research question of this scoping review has been phrased in a manner that is comprehensive in its scope and aims to facilitate an overview of the subject matter that is commensurate with the research aim: *What intersectional approaches, theories, and methodologies are used by gender research to analyze intersectional gender inequalities in the academic higher education governance?*

The PCC framework served as orientation for developing our research question. The framework was developed in the context of medical research, which limits its applicability in the social sciences (Barisoux et al., 2024). In the question of this review, the research subject encompasses the *approaches, theories, and methodologies* of international gender research studies. The content is set at the intersectional gender inequalities in higher education governance. The context is higher education, specifically universities.

The iterative process of formulating the overarching research question included an expansion of "gender" to the concept of intersectionality, to deliberately narrow down the research scope. This was done after consultation with the project's board of experts. Depending on its interpretation, intersectionality offers a valuable lens to critically examining power relations within gender perspectives (Biele Mefebue et al., 2022) in the context of higher education and research. Lastly, the

contemporary recognition and take-up of intersectionality have given rise to a substantial body of research. This is a particularly important factor within the broader context of scoping reviews. The efficacy of mapping is based upon the existence of multiple studies whose contents can be systematically extracted, analyzed, and subsequently clustered into a comprehensible overview.

3.2 Sources and Search Strategy

First, we identified a set of 150 peer-reviewed English-language journals assigned to the area of gender research within the Scopus abstract and citation database. In order to reduce the potential amount of material to be processed, the aim was to select the most important gender studies journals from the database. The list of journals was initially filtered using quantitative criteria, i.e. using the ScImago journal ranking, which is based on the number of citations per journal. The popularity of the journals was an initial indicator for selecting thirty journals as source of building our literature corpus. Subsequently, around thirty journals were selected from within the 150 journals. Gray literature, monographs, conference proceedings or omnibus volumes have been excluded from the review, which focusses on the publication format of original journal articles.

In the course of exchanges with the project's board of experts, the quality parameters for selecting journals were reconsidered and adapted. Based on the concern, whether the previously set quantitative parameters could provide any indication of the quality and innovative nature of the journal articles, and to what extent the journal selection represents the diversity of gender studies, qualitative indicators, i.e. the description of the scope of each journal, was added as selection criteria for the journals. Subsequently, all the journals were evaluated based on the description of *the aims and scope* on the publishers' websites. In addition, following the recommendation of the experts active in the field of higher education research, priority was given to journals that included positions on higher education research with a focus on gender or diversity. According to their self-description, the scope of all selected journals also includes at least one of the three research topics considered in the project: the academic labor market, knowledge production in universities, and university and higher education governance.

Ultimately, the following journals were selected to form the basis for our literature review based on the criteria and considerations described above:

1. *Journal of Women and Gender in Higher Education* (ISSN: 2637-9112)
2. *Affilia Journal of Women and Social Work* (ISSN: 15523020)
3. *Journal of Diversity in Higher Education* (ISSN: 1938-8926)
4. *Gender and Education* (ISSN: 13600516)
5. *Gender and Society* (ISSN: 0891-2432)
6. *Journal of Blacks in Higher Education* (ISSN: 1077-3711)
7. *Social Psychology of Education* (1381-2890)
8. *The International Journal of Diversity in Education* (ISSN: 2327-0020)
9. *Women in Higher Education* (ISSN: 2331-5466)
10. *Race & Class* (ISSN: 03063968)
11. *Gender in Management* (ISSN: 1754-2413)
12. *European Journal of Politics and Gender* (ISSN: 2515-1088)

13. *Advancing Women in Leadership* (ISSN: 1093-7099)
14. *Journal of Women and Minorities in Science and Engineering* (ISSN: 1072-8325)
15. *Signs: Journal of Women in Culture and Society* (ISSN: 15456943)
16. *European Journal of Women Studies* (ISSN: 1350-5068)
17. *Gender Work and Organization* (ISSN: 1468-0432)
18. *Journal of Homosexuality* (ISSN: 0091-8369)
19. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship* (ISSN: 1756-6266)
20. *Gender, Place, and Culture* (ISSN: 0966-369X)
21. *Men and Masculinities* (ISSN: 1097-184X)
22. *Equality, Diversity and Inclusion* (ISSN: 2040-7149)
23. *Politics and Gender* (ISSN: 1743-923X)
24. *Journal of Sex Research* (ISSN: 0022-4499)
25. *Journal of Gender Studies* (ISSN: 14653869)
26. *Ethnic and Racial Studies* (ISSN: 01419870)
27. *Feminist Criminology* (ISSN: 1557-086X)
28. *Feminist Formations* (ISSN: 2151-7363)
29. *Innovative Higher Education* (ISSN: 0742-5627)
30. *Journal of Women, Politics & Policy* (ISSN: 1554-4788)

As a first step to develop the search strings, the key tool to find and retrieve relevant journal articles from the journal database, an initial list of keywords was developed (later used as search terms). The keywords were identified in existing articles based on a first search in *Web of Science*, in which the "Research Area" was set to Gender Studies and the search queries ("governance" OR "policy" OR "policies") AND ("Higher Education" OR "university" OR "academ*" OR "facult*") were used. These were then clustered thematically without hierarchization using a mind map. The mind map was supplemented with additional keywords from the GESIS literature database Lit@CEWS¹ and finally, complemented by terminology suggested by the research team and the project's board of experts. The terminology for the search string was tested for results in two databases several times and implemented in both, British English and American English spelling.

¹ See <https://www.gesis.org/cews/recherche-und-beratung/recherche-tools/literatur>, last checked on 23.03.2026.

Figure 1: Mind Map of keywords for “higher education governance” in preparation of the search string composition

The search strings consist of keywords/search terms linked with Boolean operators to refine the search. The operators AND, OR, and NOT are used. The search string is organized in the following logic: The first part of the string sets the framework in academia by the terms *Universit* OR */Higher Education OR Academ**. This is followed by the second part of search terminology which asks for theoretical terminology of gender studies research, for example *femin* OR wom* OR masc* OR intersect* OR divers**. The third part of the search string contains topical terminology, which is associated with higher education governance, some examples are “govern*” “transformation” OR “organi* change” OR “organi*ation” OR “reform”. The full search string contains significantly more terms.

The search strategy complies with the 2019 *Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies* review guideline (McGowan et al., 2016). The guideline serves as an aid in creating search strings that are as precise and comprehensible as possible.

The entire search strategy used for the Web of Science database is shown below:

(“HIGHER EDUCATION” OR “ACADEM*” OR “UNIVERSIT*” OR “Science*”) AND (“diversit*” OR “gender” OR “femin*” OR “wom*” OR “masc*” OR “queer*” OR “LGB*” OR “gay” OR “homo*” OR “intersect*” OR “binar*” OR “decolon*”) AND (“govern*” “transformation” OR “organi* change” OR “organi*ation” OR “reform” OR “neoliberal mode of science” OR “neoliberal*” OR “entrepreneurial” OR “decision-making” OR “diversity polic*” OR “diversity management” OR “polic*” OR “equal opportunit*” OR “gender equality” OR “inclus*” OR “practice” OR “regulation*” OR “family friendly polic*” OR “quota” OR “anti-discrimination” OR “DEI” OR “DIE” OR “resistance to change” OR “resources” OR “financing” OR “discrimination” OR “autonom*” OR “liberalism” OR “academic freedom” OR “ranking*” OR “competition” OR “management” OR “controlling” OR “quality management” OR “excellence” OR “evaluation*” OR “professionalism” OR “monitor*” OR “data collection” OR “senate” OR “leadership” OR “legislation*” OR “committee*” OR “board” OR “managerial*” OR “agreement*” OR “framework” OR “performance agreement” OR “new public management” OR “diversity office*” OR “public management” OR “research management” OR “governance polic*” OR “academic system” OR “governance mechanism*” OR “organi*ation theor*” OR “isomorphism” OR “organi*ational culture”) NOT (“student*” OR “graduate*” OR “undergraduate” OR “didactic*” OR “teach*” OR “school*”)

The literature databases *OpenAlex* and *Web of Science* are used for the search of articles. We selected *Web of Science* because the database is particularly suitable for complex search queries with detailed search strings and provides extensive metadata (title and abstract). However, since not all included journals are covered by the database, we repeated the search in the *OpenAlex* database. *OpenAlex* is an open-source scientific database made public in 2022. The database is equally suited for literature review searches because it has significantly more sources than other databases such as *Scopus* or *Web of Science* (Culbert et al., 2024). *OpenAlex* identifies less prominent journals such as the *Journal of Blacks in Higher Education* or the *Journal of Women and Gender in Higher Education*. We did not consider the *Scopus* database for licensing reasons. Although *Google Scholar* has the largest number of sources globally it is not suitable for a systematic literature search query with precise search strings and was therefore excluded.

To ensure comparability of the results from the two databases, the search strings were adapted to the search parameters of the respective databases, i.e. *OpenAlex*. *Web of Science* recognizes truncations in searches, but *OpenAlex* does not allow truncations and automatically searches for matches based on word stems and can only identify terms if the whole word is legible. Word stems such as “wom” for *woman* or “masc” for masculine are not recognized. The search strings were adjusted according to these criteria. In addition, *OpenAlex* cannot process search strings above the character limit of 2,048 characters, including spaces and URLs. For this reason, the search strings

entered in their entirety in the Web of Science database must be broken down to run the identical search in the OpenAlex database.

In order to ensure comparability of search in the two databases, which have different search parameters, we conducted searches exclusively based on the title of an article, instead of title and abstract. The aim of this scoping review is not to identify gaps in the research literature corpus, but to provide an overview and map out existing theories and methodologies to analyze the subject of interest. For this reason, a complete mapping of the literature, which cannot be guaranteed by a title search alone, is not relevant.

Type/location of identified study	Number of studies
Total	552
of which Web of Science	496
of which Open Alex	56
of which duplicates	176

Table 1: Overview of search results by source of database

3.3 Study Selection Criteria

The article search was concluded on June 16, 2025. Articles published after this date have not been considered in the analysis.

Inclusion	Exclusion
Higher education or university	Articles addressing non-university research organizations
Higher education governance (state regulation, competition, external stakeholder guidance, academic self-governance, and managerial self-governance)	Policies, programs or management decisions that do not address higher education governance, articles focusing on didactics or teaching in universities
Articles on higher education leadership decisions	Articles focusing primarily on career trajectories
Articles addressing a gender perspective, including woman or female	Not addressing gender as a social positionality
Gender and more intersecting social positionings considered in the article, e.g. ethnicity, social origin, age, disability, queerness, (intersectionality does not need to be named as such), OR intersecting <i>systems of oppression</i> on the institutional level	Not addressing gender and more intersecting positionings, or intersecting systems of oppression on the institutional level

Original articles, research articles	Conference reports, obituaries, grey literature, book reviews, editorials, interviews
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Table 2: Overview of criteria for inclusion and exclusion of articles

All articles, but duplicate items, have been included in the first screening based on the topical relevance to the research question formulated for the subject of university and higher education governance and in conjunction with the criterion of addressing gender and intersectional social positions and/or intersecting *systems of oppression*. The subject area of higher education governance is defined based on a definition developed for the search string, particularly on the *governance equalizer*-concept (Lange & Schimank 2007; Schimank 2007), see above. It also guided the allocation of the articles to the designated subject area.

Articles that do not address the broader topic of university and higher education governance such as state regulation, competition, external stakeholder guidance, academic self-governance, and managerial self-governance are excluded from the review. This also holds true for articles that do not include any reference to intersectional dimensions including gender, or feminist or gender or an institutional *systems of oppression approach*. Articles not written in English are also excluded from the review. Moreover, non-original journal articles, such as book reviews, editorials, interviews, obituaries, and conference reports are excluded from the scoping review. Articles that deal primarily with gender issues in teaching, university didactics, etc. are also excluded, unless they are framed in the context of higher education governmental decisions or policies.

This review focuses on an institutional perspective, individual career trajectories or experiences that are biographical or essayistic in nature and focus on self-reflection are only included if they are framed a) in the context of policies or governmental decisions, b) exemplify the impact of such measures, c) include the discussion of institutional climate. Articles on university leadership have been included if they discuss leadership styles or managerial decisions. Studies that discuss specific university members such as researchers, students and administrative employees are included if they are presented as stakeholders, target groups of programs, as involved in policies and governmental measures or if as positioned to or against programs, policies and measures (e.g. diversity, equity, inclusion programs).

3.4 Software and study Selection Process

Following the identification of studies in Web of Science and OpenAlex, the research team used the *EPPI-Reviewer 6²* software for all steps of the screening process. EPPI-Reviewer is a web-based application for managing, documenting and analyzing data from systematic literature reviews, developed by the Institute of Education at the University College London (Thomas et al., 2023) and is hosted by the EPPI Centre of UCL. The program simplifies the identification of duplicate items and documents the screening process results for each researcher involved. Metadata of literature items can be imported, and duplicates are automatically identified using AI to make the sorting of studies more efficient. Furthermore, the program can be used to highlight relevant terms within titles and abstracts, which are then automatically documented. In addition to sorting literature items into include or exclude categories, the program allows and documents specifications of the reasons for the decision taken on each literature item. EPPI-Reviewer has an integrated process documentation

² See <https://eppi.ioe.ac.uk>, last checked on 24.03.2026.

tool that generates overview tables to map out the full screening process for each review. An additional tool, the EPPI-Mapper was used for visualizing “maps” of research evidence at the final stage of the coding process.

The categories assigned to the studies in the first screening run within the EPPI-Reviewer software are , "*Include on Title and Abstract*" for articles that fully match the inclusion criteria, and "*Include for second opinion*", if, after the first reading of title and abstract by one researcher in the team, there is uncertainty about the relevance of the study to seek a second opinion. When studies are excluded for formal reasons, we assigned the respective categories, e.g. *Exclude on Editorial, Book Review, Obituary Or Report*, generally for articles which didn't present original research. The category *Exclude on Topic* was assigned if the content of the article does not match the research topic, and *Exclude on Target Group*, if the journal article deals with university populations or individuals outside the context of university and higher education governance.

Metadata of the initial 552 journal articles were imported into EPPI Reviewer, which flagged 176 articles as duplicate, which were checked and removed from the corpus of journal articles to enter the first screening exercise. 376 journal articles were included in the first screening according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria described above by two to three researchers carrying out the screening. Two screening rounds were carried out: In the first round, the titles and abstracts of the articles were screened, using a double-blind review process, i.e. titles and abstracts are screened independently by reviewers one and two. At the end of the screening process, the results were compared. Any disagreements regarding the inclusion or exclusion of articles were discussed. If disagreement persisted, a third researcher, and expert on the topic, was consulted for assessment and decision. This approach resulted in three scenarios: (1) a clear and unanimous decision by two reviewers to include the article based on the title and abstract. (2) No direct unanimous decision by both reviewers regarding the inclusion of the text. (3) If, after discussing the title and abstract, the two reviewers remained in disagreement regarding its inclusion or exclusion, a third reviewer was consulted, and the decision regarding the article's categorization was made by majority vote.

The resulting set of articles deemed eligible after the first screening was shared with one topical expert outside the research team who was asked to identify articles that could potentially be excluded based on the topical criteria in title and abstract. A final decision on further articles to be excluded was taken by the research team of the project.

At the end of the first screening of title and abstract of articles on higher education governance, 95 articles were included, and 281 articles were excluded.

For the second screening, the reviewers used the articles' full text to identify details for assessing their eligibility based on the formal and topical criteria described above and decide whether the respective article should finally be excluded or included in the corpus to be reviewed. The full texts, which were uploaded to the EPPI-Reviewer program, were either found as open access files or were made accessible for this research with the help of the institute's library. In the second screening, one researcher carried out the mayor part of the eligibility assessment in constant exchange with a second researcher. A second reviewer was consulted, when necessary, e.g. if any doubt or uncertainty about the assignment of a literature item arose. All researchers involved in the screening of the full texts were asked to write “fieldwork notes” during the screening, see chapter 4 of this research protocol.

In the second screening, articles were assigned to the following categories in EPPI-Reviewer: *Include on Full Study*, the entire study fits the working definition of university and higher education governance and the research question in terms of content, *Include for Second Opinion*, further discussion in the research team is needed, or *Exclude on Topic*, if the content of the study does not fit the defined criteria or the topic of university and higher education governance is not the focus of the study.

Exclude on Target Group, if the article deals with university populations or individuals outside the context of higher education governance, *Exclude on Type of Text*, if the article does not present original research or reflections, and *Exclude on lack of Gender Dimension and Intersectionality* if the study does not elaborate on gender in conjuncture with other dimensions of intersectionality or intersecting *systems of oppression*. In cases of uncertainty, expertise from outside the project's research team was included in form of a group of academics who support the project from the onset.

After completing the full-text screening, 50 studies were included and 45 more studies excluded from the next step of the scoping review exercise.

Figure 2: Flow chart providing a full overview of the screening process and results

4 Data Extraction

The relevant data was extracted in EPPI-Reviewer from the full text articles included in the scoping review by three researchers independently, using the data extraction scheme/ coding scheme, developed by the project team. The coding scheme was developed in two steps: first deductively, based on the definition of university and higher education governance and the overarching research question for the scoping review. Four broad data extraction/coding³ categories were specified to form the basic structure for the extraction of information: subject area of investigation, gender+ theories, intersectionality, methods, and metadata. After concluding the first screening on title and abstract, the basic structure was elaborated and revised inductively, based on the topical considerations, particularly on the subject area of investigation. To structure the topical scope of literature we opted for a three-level model of higher education governance. This model illustrates the multi-level nature of control mechanisms at universities (macro, meso, and micro). Studies that address government regulations or illustrate major global trends in higher education organization are coded at the macro level. The meso-level describes internal university governance processes. The micro level, on the other hand, deals with individual higher education policy actors and their role in larger governance processes. The three levels cannot be considered separately from one another. Overlaps become apparent when a study addresses several levels and are coded accordingly.

How the articles present “intersectionality” explicitly or implicitly, is another core interest of the analysis. The coding scheme differentiates between the explicit mention of the term intersectionality and analyzing social positionings without explicitly referring to the term. Intersectionality can be used as both, a theoretical perspective as well as guiding tool for the methodological design and implementation of qualitative or quantitative empirical research (Bauer, 2021; Cooke & Nyhagen, 2024; Misra et al., 2021). Thus, we build the coding scheme to allow the extraction of information from each article to distinguish whether intersectionality is considered as part of a theoretical framework or as part of the methodology, or both. Intersectionality was also coded when there is an understanding of intersectionality, either explicitly or implicitly, according to Patricia Hill Collins’ Systems of Oppression. To better understand how sustainably and pervasively intersectionality is implemented in a text, we determine the extent to which the study understands intersectionality as both a methodological and theoretical basis. Intersectionality in the method is coded when intersectionality has been incorporated into the research design, for example as part of statistical surveys or as a perspective in the research question. Intersectionality as theory, on the other hand, is coded when intersectionality can be considered one or the only analytical framework of the research. Through this different operationalization of intersectionality, we want to ensure that studies are identified that do not only superficially use the concept. These studies can serve as best practice examples of the implementation of intersectionality in relation to higher education from a gender perspective.

In the EPPI-Reviewer program, codes are assigned per journal article, i.e. literature item. Therefore, any quantitative analysis of the review exercise can be done in two ways: with reference to the number of studies to which a specific code has been assigned, or with reference to the number of codes

³ In this protocol, we use the terms “information extraction”, “data extraction” and “coding” interchangeably because methodologically, they refer to the same process of identification and assignment of text, that corresponds to one or more conceptual categories of the scheme that operationalizes the research question.

distributed among the literature items. In general, we will report on results of our analysis with reference to the number of literature items because any numerical analysis can be put into perspective with the overall number of articles analyzed.

Another part of the coding scheme is the section on gender theories. Gender theories and theoretical frameworks refer to theories that conceptually address and outline or reflect on gender. The gender theories that have been included are very broad and are based on the major theoretical divisions in gender studies. The selection of gender theories depicted in the coding scheme is based on a handbook for gender studies (Becker & Kortendiek, 2010). We decided to use broad theoretical frameworks in the coding scheme, as an overly detailed approach would make an analysis of the texts unfit for interdisciplinary dialogue. More specific theories are coded if they belong to a broader theoretical school of thought.

We coded common social science methods for the scoping review analysis. We distinguish between literature-based, qualitative, quantitative, and mixed- or multi- method approaches. As with gender theories, not all methods can be included in their entirety. Under the subcode *ethnography* within the code *qualitative methods*, we also include autoethnographic methods. Within the coding scheme, mixed methods are understood not only as a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods, but also the use of different qualitative methods or different quantitative methods. These combinations of methods that produce qualitative or quantitative data are often described as multi-method approaches (Anguera et al., 2018).

The last part of the coding scheme is the metadata. It aggregates the publication year into a timespan starting from the 1980s in increments of five years until 2025. In addition, the country of affiliation of each author named in the study was extracted.

The full coding scheme applied for extracting information from the studies on the topic of university governance is provided in the next chapter. Further explanations have been added to a code during the process of coding the studies as seen necessary by each reviewer and the additions shared and discussed in the research team. Any concern during the process was shared between reviewers and has been resolved through discussion in the team or by consulting additional researchers. In addition to schema-based information extraction, general and article-specific observations on the material were recorded in a continuously updated fieldwork log during the coding process. These observations are used for analysis in the production of the scoping review journal article following the review and serve to ensure transparency and traceability of the coding process.

4.1 Coding Scheme for Data Extraction

Fundamental Elements of the Study.

Intersectionality explicitly mentioned in the study: yes/no

The study explicitly refers to the term intersectionality, i.e., it mentions it in the text as its own working basis, regardless of the facet or foundation on which this term is used.

Data Basis from the "global North": yes/no

The data basis of the study or the contribution of a study is located exclusively in the Global North (Europe, USA, Canada)

Object of Study: Higher education governance

Macro-Level

The macro level describes the state regulation to which universities are subject (university laws, academic freedom). Mechanisms that lie outside the self-administration of the university. For example, a politically motivated shift in power through reforms can lead to stronger top-down control. Equality often becomes a secondary battleground for power struggles, e.g., in appointment procedures, etc.

Goal-oriented external control and policies

Higher education reforms and concepts such as New Public Management; increasingly competitive orientation of universities, anchoring and strengthening of external control by actors such as the university council, and increasing professionalization of internal organizational management levels.

Market mechanisms and competition

The effects of market mechanisms on universities, e.g., research funding/excellence programs, prestige, symbolic capital, etc. In addition, articles deal with the way universities compete, especially under the conditions of increasingly market-oriented control of the higher education system. This competition affects various areas and has concrete implications for governance, e.g., the management, control, and decision-making structures within universities.

Meso-Level

The meso-level at universities describes academic self-organization; (decisions made internally about academic operations, examination regulations, curriculum, research output requirements, and collegial self-organization with a high degree of autonomy for professors.

Governance structure of the university

Design of internal organizational decision-making processes and decision-making powers, resources, and incentives for members. Which committee or actors are involved in designing and introducing new units, and who is informed?

Internal hierarchy

The internal hierarchy in university governance describes the organizational levels and power relations within a university, i.e., who has which decision-making powers, responsibilities, and roles, with hybrid forms and parallels reflecting the reality of governance (Oberschelp, 2023, p. 16).

Control via policies

Control of the governance structure via regulations within the university.

Data (basis), data-supported governance

The article deals with the collection of data that is used as a basis for governance decisions and policies.

Attitudes of stakeholders (interest groups) toward equality

The attitudes or criticism of various university groups about equality and diversity work.

Micro-Level

The micro level encompasses the internal organizational level within a university, the management and decision-making processes in departments, faculties, institutes, and individual working groups, as well as those of individuals.

Requirements for leadership positions

The study examines the leadership style and tasks of individuals who make governance decisions at the university. It also discusses the prerequisites for successful leadership.

Role of gender in leadership positions

The study specifically addresses the role and impact of gender and gender identity in leadership positions and leadership styles.

Competence, awareness, and knowledge of leadership actors

The study examines training opportunities and raising awareness among managers, particularly with regard to gender knowledge.

(Gender) Theoretical Approaches

Essentialism, difference theory: *Assumption: Gender differences are natural or stable.*

Biological gender theory: *Gender differences are based on biological differences (hormones, genes, anatomy).*

Difference feminism: *Femininity is an independent quality that should be viewed positively, not as a deviation from masculinity.*

Social Constructivism and Deconstruction

Assumption: Gender is conveyed through education, learning, and adaptation to social expectations.

Socialization theories/educational processes

Social constructivist gender theory: *Gender is "made" through socialization, role learning, and social attributions. (Stereotypes)*

Doing Gender (West & Zimmerman), Judith Butler: *Performativity of gender: Gender is not a characteristic, but a performative social practice in everyday life. Gender is created through repeated actions; there is no "true" gender behind the performance.*

Embodiment: *The body is not only biological, but also socially and culturally shaped; gender is embodied*

Structuralist and Materialist Theories

Assumption: Gender is inscribed in social and economic power relations.

Materialist & Marxist feminism (critique of capitalism): *Patriarchy is intertwined with capitalism; the oppression of women arises from class relations. Gender relations are linked to economic conditions such as wage labor, property, and reproduction.*

Bourdieu's theory of symbolic power: *Gender orders reproduce themselves through habitual, symbolic practices (e.g., "male domination").*

Poststructuralist and Deconstructivist Theories

Assumption: Gender is fluid, discursively constructed, and cannot be fixed.

Queer Theory/Transfeminism: *Challenges normative ideas of gender and sexuality; identity is unstable and open. Links feminist theory with transactivist perspectives, for example, emphasizes gender as diverse and self-determined.*

Postmodern feminisms: *Rejection of fixed identities and truths; diversity, contradictions, and ambiguities are at the forefront.*

Posthumanist gender theories: *New Materialisms, Situated Knowledge, and positioning (Haraway)*

Theories of Masculinity

Hegemonic masculinity (R. W. Connell): *Core idea: There is not one form of masculinity, but several. Hegemonic masculinity is the dominant, socially accepted form (e.g., white, heterosexual, assertive). Other forms of masculinity (e.g., homosexual, "soft" or migrant masculinity) are subordinate or marginalized.*

Multiple masculinities: *Core idea: Builds on Connell's approach: Masculinity is not universal, but diverse, situation- and context- dependent. Men perform different masculinities depending on social class, ethnicity, sexuality, or age. Interactions between forms of masculinity are emphasized. Allows for differentiated analyses, e.g., of queer, migrant, or non-Western masculinities. Particularly used in intersectional research.*

Postcolonial and Decolonial Theories

Core idea: Due to colonial history, education and science systems are globally permeated by Western hegemonic power structures. These are recognized and should be overcome or deconstructed. Colonial structures are persistent and are carried on consciously or subconsciously.

Critical race theory: *CRT seeks to reveal that racism is not an individual attitude, but a system that is structurally embedded in various institutions (e.g., state institutions).*

Postcolonial Feminism: *Criticism of Western-influenced feminism emphasizes global inequality and colonial continuities.*

Intersectional Perspectives: *Assumption: Gender cannot be viewed in isolation but is related to other axes of power that overlap and intersect.*

Intersectionality and Theory: *Intersectionality serves as the theoretical basis for a study.*

Intersectionality and Method: *Intersectionality is methodologically represented in a study or included in the research design.*

Intersectionality (Crenshaw): *Gender intersects with categories such as ethnicity, class, sexuality—and shapes social inequalities.*

Social Positionings

Race/ethnicity and gender: *e.g., also in Black Feminism, or migrant women researchers, any "othering process" in relation to racialization, religion, cultural "othering"*

Social class and gender: *e.g., working-class women academics*

Disabilities and gender: *e.g., ableism in academia*

Age and gender: *e.g., ageism and female academics*

Queerness and gender: *e.g., queer female academics*

Systems of Oppression (perspective which is critical of power-relations)

Intersectional systems of oppression are structurally embedded and mutually reinforcing forms of domination that operate simultaneously across multiple social dimensions and levels, including the individual, cultural, institutional, and structural (Hill Collins, 2017; Simien, 2007).

Methods

Literature reviews

Systematic reviews: *The study presents a systematic literature review, e.g., a scoping review or another form from the family of systematic literature review methods.*

Meta-studies: *The study is a meta-study (also meta-analysis) if it is a quantitative literature review in which the results of several empirical studies are statistically combined to calculate an aggregate effect or correlation.*

Theoretical work/essay: *The article reflects on and discusses a question/subject with reference to secondary literature. Theoretical-conceptual essays without their own data collection basis belong to this category.*

Qualitative Methods

Discourse analysis, document evaluation: *The study focuses primarily on the method of document evaluation or presents the results of discourse analysis. This methodological focus may have been chosen as the sole focus or may form a methodological focus in combination with other methods of data collection/data evaluation. This does not refer to an introduction to the topic or a discussion of the current literature on the topic in the form of an introductory subchapter of a text; rather, the article goes beyond a literature review of the subject matter/question being addressed.*

Ethnography, including participant observation, autoethnography: *The study contains methodological explanations of ethnographic methods such as participant observation, autoethnography, or similar. Correspondence and dialogical formats via email in the sense of autoethnography are included here, as well as field research reports and personal diary evaluations.*

Interviews, e.g., (professional) biographical interviews, expert interviews, problem-focused interviews, group interviews, focus groups, etc.: *The study describes any type of interview method for the production of qualitative data, e.g., narratives in oral or written form, including biographical or professional biographical interviews, problem-centered interview methods, or group interviews.*

Case studies: *The study describes a case study, i.e., a detailed investigation of a single case or several selected cases (e.g., an organization, a project, a person, an event) within their real social context.*

Quantitative Methods

Analysis of statistical data: *The study focuses on a secondary evaluation of statistical or quantitative data, e.g., from personnel statistics, income data for assessing the gender pay gap, research funding statistics, or similar.*

Standardized surveys: *The article describes the implementation of a standardized survey, e.g., online survey, experiment, or similar, and presents a quantitative evaluation of the findings.*

Quantitative content analysis: *The article describes a statistical evaluation of qualitative data, e.g., through topic modeling or similar methods. This also includes quantitative evaluations of social media or other digital behavioral data using quantitative methods.*

Mixed Methods

The study systematically combines or integrates different methodological approaches in order to achieve a more comprehensive understanding of a research topic. Different types of data, collection and analysis methods are interlinked. This category includes mixed- and multi-method research designs.

Combination of qualitative/qualitative methods: *The study combines different qualitative methods within a single study (e.g., participant observation and guided interviews, collective writing, auto-ethnographic methods) for the collection and evaluation of data.*

Combination of qualitative and quantitative methods: *The study combines qualitative and quantitative methods (e.g., statistical calculations including from secondary sources, regressions, experiments, participant observation and guided interviews, collective writing, auto-ethnographic methods) for the collection and evaluation of data.*

Combination of quantitative/quantitative methods: *The study combines different quantitative methods (e.g., statistical calculations, regressions, experiments) for data collection and analysis.*

Metadata

Year of publication: *Year of publication without month (publication year), not date of online early access.*

- 1980-1985
- 1986-1990
- 1991-1995
- 1996-2000
- 2001-2005
- 2006-2010
- 2011-2015
- 2016-2020
- 2021-2025

Country of the Authors' Institution (Affiliation): *Country of each author's institution, including co-authors, to be recorded in the metadata. This should be extractable from the "affiliation" field. The aim is to evaluate the overall distribution of countries per ScR topic. Further subdivision, e.g., by subtopic, is not necessary.*

Additionally, an analysis of the distribution of included articles among the journals was done on the basis of each article's metadata information and not based on the assignment of the article to a code by researchers.

4.2 Fieldwork Notes

In addition to data extraction using the extraction scheme we recorded general and article-specific observations on the material in a field protocol, which we kept continuously during the coding process. These observations were used for the discussion section of the article following the review but also serve the purpose of transparency to ensure the traceability of the coding process.

- During the coding process, it became clear that a sharp distinction between theory and methodology cannot always be made, especially regarding the way intersectional analysis was implemented. In these cases, I (Meltem Yalcin) double coded (both theory and method).
- All intersecting positionalities that I coded, I understood as umbrella terms. For example, the code *ethnicity* which we used as a category instead of 'race', not a common terminology in Germany, also encompasses religious attribution, which can lead to racialization. The code *disability* also includes chronic illnesses, mental illnesses, and neurodivergence.
- The code set that we created for gender theories is very broad. Theories of feminist institutionalism and organizational theory (e.g. Acker) are particularly dominant in the articles of university and higher education governance. Depending on their interpretation of the concepts, I assigned these theories to the codes *structuralist and materialist theories*, *social constructivism*, *deconstruction*, and both. I made this decision on an article-specific basis.
- Articles that represent a purely binary understanding of gender that is not questioned or contextualized were coded as *gender essentialist*.
- The main difficulty I encountered in coding studies on university and higher education governance was staying within the sharp boundaries of the levels (macro, meso, and micro), which we defined and artificially set for the coding scheme. Most articles address governance at several levels; however, these connections are not always visible in our coding scheme. For example, individual actors influence policies and are, in turn, included or promoted in networks at the macro level through bottom-up processes. In these cases, I coded all or several levels per article.
- The *micro level* code in the coding scheme does not mention a bottom-up governance approach. If articles dealt with this form of governance, for example in an activist context, I assigned them the code *attitudes of stakeholders* (university populations) towards policies and programs (e.g. in diversity and equity).

4.3 Synthesis and Presentation of Results

The codes per journal article have been synthesized into categorial code-based tables, using an automated mapping function within the program EPPI-Reviewer, named EPPI-Mapper. The coding maps produced by the software give first indications for the analysis of the extracted information and are primarily depicted quantitatively. The coding is presented in the form of bar charts, tables, cross tables and evidence maps. We use quantitative results as one first level of analysis of the results of the scoping review. In addition, we extract the lists and tables with the coded text per article as direct quotations per category. This material is qualitative text passages, which we use to illustrate the quality of our scoping review findings.

5 Ethics and Dissemination

The subject of this research is a secondary analysis of published journal articles, from which we extract information of interest to respond to our research question. We identified approaches, theories and methodologies of international gender studies published in peer-reviewed journals, which need to meet standards of research ethics and good scientific practice. Our scoping review is not subject to a research ethics assessment, because we conduct a secondary analysis of published original research, without accessing the original data underlying the publications.

There are no violations of rights that would prevent the implementation of the project or use of the results, such as intellectual property rights, patent rights, or similar. The necessary licenses granting access to electronic databases are available, and access to articles behind paywalls have been purchased for the implementation of the scoping review.

The scoping review process is supported by a board of experts uniting 15 academics from the fields of higher education research and gender studies, who support the project team with expertise in developing the research questions, the terminology for the search strings, and the selection of journals and articles. The research team and all experts associated with our research work were granted access to information about the project at any stage, including the interim results, which were discussed in two workshops. Interdisciplinary collaborations are particularly well suited for building critical expertise that facilitates the exchange of knowledge and the development of skills in all academic disciplines.

The final results of our scoping review are expected to be published in form of a research article at the end of 2026. In addition, the results are presented at two conferences in the field of German higher education research in winter 2025 and spring 2026.

6 Limitations

The aim of this scoping review is to map gender studies' perspective on governance in universities and institutions of higher education. This scoping review does not focus on identifying research gaps in order to close them in a targeted manner, nor does it critically evaluate the results of the included studies. We do not foresee to assess the quality of the original research that was subject to the journal articles included in the scoping review of literature. Our aim is to provide a systematic overview of existing theories and approaches to higher education with a focus on intersectionality from the perspective of international gender studies.

To narrow down the literature review of "international" gender studies, the literature search focuses on English-language journals that publish gender research. The search strategy was conducted exclusively in the Web of Science and Open Alex databases. However, the completeness of the articles indexed for individual journals cannot be guaranteed, as publishers have not fully digitized older journal issues. The focus on English-language publications also leads to a possible bias of the findings in terms of geographical location and content, as European and Anglo-American perspectives are privileged. The hegemony of existing knowledge systems is reflected in the results of this review.

The focus on journal articles turns a blind eye on relevant works published in overarching or related social science publications. Monographs, anthologies, conference proceedings, gray literature, and interview formats are not included in the search for publication formats, although these forms of publication are common in some disciplines, including in gender and intersectionality research, but also in higher education research. These practical research decisions must be taken into account when interpreting the findings of the literature review.

Finally, it is interesting that few studies were identified that explicitly address intersectionality as a theory or method in relation to disability or chronic illness. When selecting the journals, attention was paid to ensuring that gender was named as a central topic of analysis in the respective scope of interest to the journal. This may have led to relevant contributions from disability studies not being taken into account, as these may be published in other subject-specific journals that fall outside the selected search framework.

Against this background, it seems interesting to expand the selection of journals in future reviews, in terms of both thematic focus and publication languages.

7 Conclusion

The scoping review examines approaches, theories, and methodologies of international gender research studies with a particular focus on intersectional analysis of higher education governance. Scoping reviews are designed to close knowledge gaps or to provide an overview of a topic as possible (Elm et al., 2019). The aim of this scoping review is to identify power-critical and diversity-sensitive discussions on the topic of higher education governance in publications that can be classified as gender research studies. This scoping review is used to obtain an overview of positions, theories, and findings in gender research. Its results can help to push for a better integration of gender analyses into research designs in German higher education studies, and in turn can contribute to a broader theoretical foundation and practice of research and to the development of science-critical theory. This scoping review protocol serves to ensure transparency regarding the context and the research and implementation process of the scoping review.

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